

Figure 2

panel	description	Source file
2A	Mosaic image acquired on Zeiss axio imager M2	ChAt-eYFP mosaic slice 3 S1 8201 smaller.tif
2B	Serie 022 and 024 in Experiment_002 ChAT-CRE Chr2EYFP AntiChAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> analysis immuno Fig.2.docx Experiment_002 ChAT-CRE Chr2EYFP AntiChAT.lif
2C	Overlay of two confocal images	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment_002 F8211 L_OB.lif - Series021 (RGB).tif Experiment_002 F8211 L_OB.lif
2E	Cell 2, 24/11/2020 c2, 24-11-2020 001, ACSF, 1-30 control, 31-end light 50% c2, 24-11-2020 002, NBQX, DAP5, MECA, 1-30 control, 31-end light 50%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Figure 2E raster plot ACSF.xlsx Figure 2E raster plot NABQX, DAP5, MECA.xlsx c2, 24-11-2020 001.axgd c2, 24-11-2020 002.axgd
2F	<p>14 cells recorded in ACSF: c2, 24-11-2020 001, 1-30 control, 31-end light 50% c3, 24-11-2020 001, 1-31 control, 32-end light 50% c4, 24-11-2020 001, 1-30 control, 31-end light 50% c5, 24-11-2020 028, 1-30 control, 31-end light 50% c1, 23-11-2020 001, 1-30 control, 31-end light 100% c2, 23-11-2020 001, 1-30 control, 31-end light 100% c4, 19-06-2020 001, 1-29 control, 30-end light 100% c6, 19-06-2020 001, 1-30 control, 31-end light 20% c12, 11-12-2019 001, 1-30 control, 31-60 light 100% c10, 15-10-2019 002, 1-30 control, 31-end light 50% cell 1, 1-8-2019 001, 1-30 control, 31-60 light 100% cell 2, 1-8-2019 001, 1-30 control, 31-60 light 100% cell 3, 1-8-2019 003, 1-52 control, 53-100 light 100% cell 2, 24-5-2019 001, 1-30 control, 31-end light 100%</p> <p>5 cells recorded in NBQX-DAP5-MECA: c1, 23-11-2020 002, 1-30 control, 31-end light 100% c2, 23-11-2020 002, 1-30 control, 31-end light 100% c2, 24-11-2020 002, 1-30 control, 31-end light 50% c4, 24-11-2020 003, 1-30 control, 31-end light 50% c5, 24-11-2020 030, 1-30 control, 31-end light 50%</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fig.2F Data 2s increase in spike F in ACSF.xlsx Fig.2F Data 2s increase in spike F in NAM.xlsx <p>Raw data in folders: 14 cells recorded in ACSF</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> c1, 23-11-2020 001.axgd c2, 23-11-2020 001.axgd c2, 24-11-2020 001.axgd c3, 24-11-2020 001.axgd c4, 19-06-2020 001.axgd c4, 24-11-2020 001.axgd c5, 24-11-2020 028.axgx c6, 19-06-2020 001.axgd c10, 15-10-2019 002.axgd c12, 11-12-2019 001.axgd cell 1, 1-8-2019 001.axgd cell 2, 1-8-2019 001.axgd cell 2, 24-5-2019 001.axgd cell 3, 1-8-2019 003.axgd <p>5 cells recorded in NBQX, DAP5, MECA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> c1, 23-11-2020 002.axgd c2, 23-11-2020 002.axgd c2, 24-11-2020 002.axgd c4, 24-11-2020 003.axgd c5, 24-11-2020 030.axgd
2G	Cell 2, 24/5/2019 002: ACSF, light 100% Cell 2, 24/5/2019 003: same during scopolamine wash-in. Histogram scopo episodes 8-27	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> cell 2, 24-5-2019 002.axgd cell 2, 24-5-2019 003.axgd Figure 2G histogram.xlsx Figure 2G histogram scopolamine.xlsx

<p>2H</p>	<p>21 cells recorded in ACSF:</p> <p>cell 1, 24-5-2019 005, light 100% at t=5s cell 2, 24-5-2019 002, light 100% cell 3, 28-5-2019 001 and 003, light 100% cell 1, 1-8-2019 002, light 40% cell 2, 1-8-2019 002, light 100% cell 3, 1-8-2019 001, light 100% c22, 15-10-2019 003, light 50% c44, 15-10-2019 002, light 100% c12, 11-12-2019 003, light 100% c29, 30-10-2019 031, light 100% c4, 19-06-2020 002, light 100% c5, 19-06-2020 002, light 100% c6, 19-06-2020 002, light 50% c3, 24-11-2020 002, light 50% c4, 24-11-2020 002, light 70% c5, 24-11-2020 029, light 50% c2, 30-11-2020 001, light 100% c1, 3-12-2020 001, light 100% c2, 3-12-2020 001, light 100% c4, 3-12-2020 001, light 100% c2, 10-12-2020 001, light 100%</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fig.2H Data 15s excitation time course ACSF n=21.xlsx • Raw data for 21 cells : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 3-12-2020 001.axgd • c2, 3-12-2020 001.axgd • c2, 10-12-2020 001.axgd • c2, 30-11-2020 001.axgd • c3, 24-11-2020 002.axgd • c4, 3-12-2020 001.axgd • c4, 19-06-2020 002.axgd • c4, 24-11-2020 002.axgd • c5, 19-06-2020 002.axgd • c5, 24-11-2020 029.axgx • c6, 19-06-2020 002.axgd • c12, 11-12-2019 003.axgd • c22, 15-10-2019 003.axgd • c29, 30-10-2019 031.axgd • c44, 15-10-2019 002.axgd • cell 1, 1-8-2019 002.axgd • cell 1, 24-5-2019 005.axgd • cell 2, 1-8-2019 002.axgd • cell 2, 24-5-2019 002.axgd • cell 3, 1-8-2019 001.axgd • cell 3, 28-5-2019 001.axgd • cell 3, 28-5-2019 003.axgd
<p>2I</p>	<p>11 cells in NAM:</p> <p>c1, 10-12-2020 002, light 75% c2, 24-11-2020 003, light 50% c3, 24-11-2020 005, light 50% c1, 23-11-2020 003, light 100% c2, 23-11-2020 003, light 100% c4, 19-06-2020 003, light 100% c5, 19-06-2020 003, light 100% c6, 19-06-2020 003, light 50% c12, 11-12-2019 004, light 100% c22, 15-10-2019 004, light 100% cell 3, 28-5-2019 004, light 100%</p> <p>8 cells in scopo or atro:</p> <p>cell 3, 28-5-2019 005, light 100%, scopolamine in NAM cell 2, 24-5-2019 003, light 100%, scopo (after ep 8) in ACSF c22, 15-10-2019 004, light 50%, scopo in NAM ep 25-40 c12, 11-12-2019 005, light 100%, scopo in NAM c1, 23-11-2020 005, light 100%, atropine in NAM c2, 23-11-2020 004, light 100%, atropine in NAM c2, 24-11-2020 004, light 50%, atropine in NAM c2, 24-11-2020 007, light 70%, atropine in NAM</p>	<p>Fig.2I Data 15s PRE-POST increase in spike frequency.xlsx</p> <p>Data 11 cells in NAM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 10-12-2020 002.axgd • c1, 23-11-2020 003.axgd • c2, 23-11-2020 003.axgd • c2, 24-11-2020 003.axgd • c3, 24-11-2020 005.axgd • c4, 19-06-2020 003.axgd • c5, 19-06-2020 003.axgd • c6, 19-06-2020 003.axgd • c12, 11-12-2019 004.axgd • c22, 15-10-2019 004.axgd • cell 3, 28-5-2019 004.axgd <p>Data 8 cells in scopo or atro:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 23-11-2020 005.axgd • c2, 23-11-2020 004.axgd • c2, 24-11-2020 004.axgd • c3, 24-11-2020 007.axgd • c12, 11-12-2019 005.axgd • c22, 15-10-2019 004.axgd • cell 2, 24-5-2019 003.axgd • cell 3, 28-5-2019 005.axgd

Figure 3

panel	description	Source file
3B	Confocal Z stack	Fig.3B Experiment.lif - Series011
3C	Cell 10, 3/4/2017 control ACSF: episodes 1-10, light pulse 100% at t=5s	cell10 03042017 003.axgd Figure 3C histogram.xlsx Figure 3C raster plot.xlsx
3D	n=32 cells + mean recorded in ACSF cell11, 18072017 003, light 100%, ACSF cell12, 24072017 003+005 (ep 1-10), light 100%, ACSF cell17, 25072017 001, light 100%, ACSF cell12, 26072017 002, light 20%, ACSF cell13, 26072017 002, light 50%, ACSF cell4, 27032017 005, light 100% (at 10s, ep 6-16), ACSF cell11, 28032017 001, light 100% (ep 1-20), ACSF cell10, 03042017 003, light 100% (ep 1-15), ACSF cell9, 06042017 001, light 100%, ACSF cell7 06042017 003, light 100%, ACSF c2, 23-5-2018 002, light 50%, ep 1-18, ACSF c1, 24-5-2018 001, light 50%, ep 1-20, ACSF c3, 24-5-2018 001, light 50%, ep 1-20, ACSF c1, 29-5-2018 001, light 50%, ep 1-20, ACSF cell 9, 13-02-2019 003, light 50%, ep 1-20, ACSF cell 7, 14-02-2019 001, light 52%, ep 1-20, ACSF c12, 04-02-2020 002, light 100%, ACSF c3, 03-03-2020 002, light 100%, ACSF c11, 03-03-2020 002, light 100%, ACSF c12, 04-03-2020 002, light 100%, ACSF c1, 4-06-2020 002, light 50%, ACSF c4, 16-07-2020 001, light 50%, ACSF c5, 15-07-2020 001, light 100%, ACSF c2, 15-07-2020 001, light 60%, ACSF c1, 9-07-2020 001, light 100%, ACSF c2, 9-07-2020 001, light 50%, ACSF c2, 7-07-2020 001, light 50%, ACSF c7, 7-07-2020 001, light 70%, ACSF c8, 7-07-2020 001, light 70%, ACSF c3, 21-12-2020 026, light 90%, ACSF c5, 21-12-2020 053, light 75%, ACSF c5, 17-12-2020 033, light 50%, ACSF	Figure 3D, 32 cells+mean-15s-ACSF.xlsx Raw data 32 cells for Figure 3D: c1, 4-06-2020 002.axgd c1, 9-07-2020 001.axgd c1, 24-5-2018 001.axgd c1, 29-5-2018 001.axgd c2, 7-07-2020 001.axgd c2, 9-07-2020 001.axgd c2, 15-07-2020 001.axgd c2, 23-5-2018 002.axgd c3, 03-03-2020 002.axgd c3, 21-12-2020 026.axgd c3, 24-5-2018 001.axgd c4, 16-07-2020 001.axgd c5, 15-07-2020 001.axgd c5, 17-12-2020 033.axgd c5, 21-12-2020 053.axgd c7, 7-07-2020 001.axgd c8, 7-07-2020 001.axgd c11, 03-03-2020 002.axgd c12, 04-02-2020 002.axgd cell 7, 14-02-2019 001.axgd cell 9, 13-02-2019 003.axgd cell4 22032017 005.axgd cell7 06042017 003.axgd cell9 06042017 001.axgd cell10 03042017 003.axgd cell11 28032017 001.axgd cell11, 18072017 003.axgd cell12, 24072017 003.axgd cell12, 24072017 005.axgd cell12, 26072017 002.axgd cell13, 26072017 002.axgd cell17, 25072017 001.axgd 14 cells NAM for Figure 3F
3E	c17 25/7/2017 ACSF: cell17, 25072017 001 (see above) Atropine: cell17, 25072017 002	cell17, 25072017 002.axgd
3F	ACSF: same cells as in 3D NBQX-DAP5-MECA (=NAM):	Raw data in files: 32 cells ACSF for Figure 3D As above

	<p>c5, 16-07-2020 001, light 70% c3, 16-07-2020 002, light 50% c6, 15-07-2020 001, light 100% c4, 15-07-2020 001, light 50% c1, 5-06-2020 002, light 100% c3, 5-06-2020 001, light 100% c1, 4-06-2020 003, light 50% c19, 4-06-2020 002, light 50% c3, 03-03-2020 004, light 100% c11, 03-03-2020 003, light 100% c12, 04-02-2020 003, light 100% c1, 12-03-2020 004, ep 1-10, light 75% c2, 12-03-2020 002, ep 1-11, light 75% c4, 12-03-2020 002, ep 1-15, light 75%</p> <p>NAM+ATRO or SCOPO: cell 7, 14-02-2019 001, light 52%, scopo ep 30-50 cell 9, 13-02-2019 003, light 50%, scopo ep 25-44 c1, 24-5-2018 002, light 50%, atro ep 13-31 c3, 24-5-2018 001, light 50%, atro ep 31-46 c4, 29-5-2018 002, light 50%, atro cell12, 26072017 003, light 20%, atro cell17, 25072017 002, light 100%, atro cell12, 24072017 005 light 100%, atro ep 15-40 cell11, 18072017 004 light 100%, atro</p>	<p>14 cells NAM for Figure 3F:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 4-06-2020 003.axgd • c1, 5-06-2020 002.axgd • c1, 12-03-2020 004.axgd • c2, 12-03-2020 002.axgd • c3, 03-03-2020 004.axgd • c3, 5-06-2020 001.axgd • c3, 16-07-2020 002.axgd • c4, 12-03-2020 001.axgd • c4, 15-07-2020 001.axgd • c5, 16-07-2020 001.axgd • c6, 15-07-2020 001.axgd • c11, 03-03-2020 003.axgd • c12, 04-02-2020 003.axgd • c19, 4-06-2020 002.axgd <p>9 cells NAM+SCOPO-ATRO for Figure 3F:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 24-5-2018 002.axgd • c3, 24-5-2018 001.axgd • c4, 29-5-2018 002.axgd • cell 7, 14-02-2019 001.axgd • cell 9, 13-02-2019 003.axgd • cell11, 18072017 004.axgd • cell12, 24072017 005.axgd • cell12, 26072017 003.axgd • cell17, 25072017 002.axgd <p>Figure 3F, pre vs post ACSF, NAM, NAM+scopo-ATRO.xlsx</p>
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Figure 4

panel	description	Source file
4A	Cell 4, 8/12/2020 in ACSF Trials 1-30 : control no light Trial 31-end: light 50% at t=1s	c4, 8-12-2020 001.axgd Figure 4A histogram.xlsx Figure 4A raster plot.xlsx
4B	Average $\pm$ sem, n=17 cells recorded in ACSF cell4 27032017 003, light 100% episode 1-30 cell7 06042017 002, light 100% episode 1-30 cell11, 18072017 002, light 100% episode 1-31 cell12, 24072017 004, light 100% episode 1-30 cell13, 26072017 001, light 50% episode 1-41 cell9, 13-02-2019 002, light 50% episode 1-42 cell3 , 12-03-2019 002, light 100% episode 1-40 cell 2 , 12-03-2019 002, light 100% episode 1-50 c1, 4-06-2020 001, light 100% episode 36-67 c2, 23-5-2018 001, light 50% episode 46-79 cell12, 26072017 001, light 20% episode 1-47 c4, 8-12-2020 001, light 50% episode 31-end c3, 8-12-2020 001, light 50% episode 31-end c3, 16-12-2020 037, light 100% episode 31-end c4, 16-12-2020 044, light 80% episode 31-end	Figure 4B inhibition time course 2s n=17.xlsx Raw data for Figure 4B-C <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 4-06-2020 001.axgd • c2, 17-12-2020 011.axgd • c2, 23-5-2018 001.axgd • c3, 8-12-2020 001 Copy.axgx • c3, 16-12-2020 037.axgd • c4, 8-12-2020 001.axgd • c4, 16-12-2020 044.axgd • c5, 17-12-2020 032.axgd • c12, 04-03-2020 001.axgd • c19, 4-06-2020 001.axgd

	<p>c2, 17-12-2020 010, light 50% episode 31-end c5, 17-12-2020 032, light 50% episode 31-end</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cell 2 , 12-03-2019 002.axgd • cell 3 , 12-03-2019 002.axgd • cell 9, 13-02-2019 002.axgd • cell4 22032017 003.axgd • cell7 06042017 002.axgd • cell8 08052017 001.axgd • cell11, 18072017 002.axgd • cell12, 24072017 004.axgd • cell12, 26072017 001.axgd • cell13, 26072017 001.axgd
4C	<p>Average $\pm$ sem, n=13 cells recorded in ACSF</p> <p>10 cells indicated in bold above + c19, 4-06-2020 001, episode 1-26 control, 27-end light 50% c12, 04-03-2020 001, episode 1-23 control, 24-50 light 100% cell8 08052017 001, episode 1-32 control, 33-60 light 100%</p>	<p>Figure 4C increase in spike F n=13.xlsx</p> <p>Raw data as above</p>
4D	<p>Cell 4, 8/12/2020 in NBQX, D-AP5, MECA (=NAM)</p> <p>Trials 1-30 : control no light Trial 31-end: light 50% at t=1s</p>	<p>c4, 8-12-2020 002.axgd Figure 4D histogram.xlsx Figure 4D raster plot.xlsx</p>
4E	<p>Average $\pm$ sem, n=10 cells recorded in NBQX, D-AP5, MECA:</p> <p>c3, 22-12-2020 018, episode 1-30 control, 31-77 light 50% c2, 17-12-2020 012, episode 1-30 control, 31-80 light 50% c5, 17-12-2020 034, episode 1-30 control, 31-69 light 60% c3, 16-12-2020 038, episode 1-30 control, 31-70 light 100% c4, 16-12-2020 046, episode 1-30 control, 31-70 light 80% c3, 8-12-2020 003, episode 1-30 control, 31-68 light 50% c4, 8-12-2020 002, episode 1-30 control, 31-65 light 50% c1, 5-06-2020 001, episode 1-30 control, 31-60 light 100% c1, 12-03-2020 003, episode 1-23 control, 24-50 light 75% c1, 12-03-2020 001, episode 1-20 control, 21-50 light 75%</p>	<p>Figure 4E inhibition time course 2s blockers.xlsx</p> <p>Raw data for Figure 4E-F:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 5-06-2020 001.axgd • c1, 12-03-2020 003.axgd • c2, 12-03-2020 001.axgd • c2, 17-12-2020 012.axgd • c3, 8-12-2020 003.axgd • c3, 16-12-2020 038.axgd • c3, 22-12-2020 018.axgd • c4, 8-12-2020 002.axgd • c4, 16-12-2020 046.axgd • c5, 17-12-2020 034.axgd
4F	<p>Average $\pm$ sem, n=10 cells recorded in NBQX, D-AP5, MECA</p> <p>Same cells as above</p>	
4G	<p>Cell 4, 8/12/2020 in NBQX, D-AP5, MECA +GBZ</p> <p>Trials 1-30 : control no light Trial 31-end: light 50% at t=1s</p>	<p>c4, 8-12-2020 004.axgd Figure 4G histogram.xlsx Figure 4G raster plot.xlsx</p>
4H	<p>Average $\pm$ sem, n=8 cells recorded in NBQX, D-AP5, MECA + GBZ or ACSF + GBZ</p> <p>c7 06042017 006, light 100%, ACSF + GBZ c2, 23-5-2018 003, light 50%, ACSF+GBZ c4 27032017 007, light 100%, ACSF+GBZ</p> <p>c3, 22-12-2020 019, light 50% (ep 31-end), NAM+GBZ c2, 17-12-2020 013, light 50% (ep 31-end), NAM+GBZ c5, 17-12-2020 035, light 50% (ep 41-end), NAM+GBZ c3, 16-12-2020 039, light 100% (ep 31-end), NAM+GBZ</p>	<p>Figure 4H inhibition time course 2s GBZ.xlsx</p> <p>Raw data for Figure 4H-I</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c2, 17-12-2020 013.axgd • c2, 23-5-2018 003.axgd • c3, 16-12-2020 039.axgd

	c4, 8-12-2020 004, light 50% (ep 31-end), NAM+GBZ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c3, 22-12-2020 019.axgd • c4, 8-12-2020 004.axgd • c5, 17-12-2020 035.axgd • cell4 27032017 007.axgd • cell7 06042017 006.axgd
4I	Average $\pm$ sem, n=5 cells recorded in NBQX, D-AP5, MECA + GBZ Cells in bold above	Figure 4I increase in spike F blockers+GBZ.xlsx Raw data as above

Figure 5

panel	description	Source file
5A	Whole-cell traces from cell 2, 15/7/2020 V-clamp: c2, 15-07-2020 006 C-Clamp: c2, 15-07-2020 010	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c2, 15-07-2020 006.axgd • c2, 15-07-2020 006 Average.axgx • c2, 15-07-2020 010.axgd
5B	Morphology (serie 009 in experiment 001 21-7-2020) and firing (c4, 15-07-2020 009) of cell 4, 15/7/2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c4, 15-07-2020 009.axgd • Fig.5B Composite (RGB) PG4 15-7-2020-5.tif • Fig.5 Experiment_001 21-7-2020.lif

5C	<p>IPSC+fit from c4, 15-07-2020</p> <p>16 cells in the histogram: cell5 05-05-2017 006, Vh=0 mV, light 100% cell 7, 20-03-2019 008, Vh=0 mV, light 100% cell 8, 20-03-2019 004, Vh=0 mV, light 100% cell 7, 17-04-2019 007, Vh=0 mV, light 100% cell 2, 18-04-2019 007, Vh=0 mV, light 100% cell 3, 22-03-2019 004, Vh=0 mV, light 100% cell 4, 16-5-2019 004, Vh=0 mV, light 100% cell 9, 16-5-2019 004, Vh=0 mV, light 100% c9, 7-07-2020 005, Vh=0 mV, light 70% c2, 7-07-2020 005, Vh=-35 mV, light 50% c2, 15-07-2020 005, Vh=0 mV, light 60% c4, 15-07-2020 005, Vh=0 mV, light 50% c5, 15-07-2020 009, Vh=0 mV, light 100% c6, 15-07-2020 004, Vh=0 mV, light 100% c3, 16-07-2020 005, Vh=-30 mV, light 50% c4, 16-07-2020 004, Vh=-30 mV, light 50%</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figure 5C histogram IPSC decay.xlsx • Data for Figure 5C, photo-evoked IPSCs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c2, 7-07-2020 004.axgd • c2, 15-07-2020 005.axgd • c3, 16-07-2020 005.axgd • c4, 15-07-2020 005.axgd • c4, 16-07-2020 004.axgd • c5, 15-07-2020 009.axgd • c6, 15-07-2020 004.axgd • c9, 7-07-2020 005.axgd • cell 2, 18-04-2019 007.axgd • cell 3, 22-03-2019 004.axgd • cell 4, 16-5-2019 004.axgd • cell 7, 17-04-2019 007.axgd • cell 7, 20-03-2019 008.axgd • cell 8, 20-03-2019 004.axgd • cell 9, 16-5-2019 004.axgd • cell5 05052017 006.axgd
5D	<p>Whole cell traces from c2, 30/11/2020</p> <p>V-clamp: c2, 30-11-2020 005 (Vh=-63 mV, light 100%) C-clamp: c2, 30-11-2020 003 (light 100%)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c2, 30-11-2020 003.axgd • c2, 30-11-2020 005.axgd
5E	<p>Morphology (Experiment_001 PG4 3-12-2020) and firing (c4, 3-12-2020 004) of cell 4, 3/12/2020</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c4, 3-12-2020 004.axgd • Fig.5E PG4, 3-12-2020.tif • Fig.5 Experiment_001 PG4 3-12-2020.lif
5F	<p>ON-evoked response of cell 4, 3/12/20</p> <p>10 cells in the histogram: c4, 3-12-2020 009, Vh=-85 mV, ON stim 100 μA, ChAT c2, 10-12-2020 005, Vh=-80 mV, ON stim 70 μA, ChAT c1, 3-12-2020 008, Vh=-80 mV, ON stim 120 μA, ChAT cell 7, 20-03-2019 006, Vh=-85 mV, ON stim 70 μA, dlx cell 8, 20-03-2019 006, Vh=-75 mV, ON stim 100 μA, dlx cell 3, 22-03-2019 005, Vh=-75 mV, ON stim 150 μA, dlx cell5 05052017 017, Vh=-75 mV, ON stim 150 μA, dlx cell6 22032017 004, Vh=-75 mV, ON stim 50 μA, dlx cell 2, 18-04-2019 005, Vh=-75 mV, ON stim 30 μA, dlx cell 9, 16-5-2019 007, Vh=-85 mV, ON stim 200 μA, dlx</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figure 5F ON-evoked response.xlsx • 10 cells for histogram: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 3-12-2020 008.axgd • c2, 10-12-2020 005.axgd • c4, 3-12-2020 009.axgd • cell 2, 18-04-2019 005.axgd • cell 3, 22-03-2019 005.axgd • cell 7, 20-03-2019 006.axgd • cell 8, 20-03-2019 006.axgd • cell 9, 16-5-2019 007.axgd • cell5 05052017 017.axgd • cell6 22032017 004.axgd

Figure 6

panel	description	Source file
6A	c1, 5/6/2020, in NAM, light 100% control : 002 PIR : 003	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 5-06-2020 002.axgd • c1, 5-06-2020 003.axgd • Fig.6A Histograms.xlsx
6B	7 cells in dlx, 3 cells in ChAT. Control = NAM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fig.6B data points.xlsx • raw data for Fig.6B:

	<p>c12, 04-02-2020 003 cont and c12, 04-02-2020 004 PIR (after ep 15) c3, 03-03-2020 004 cont and c3, 03-03-2020 005 PIR c11, 03-03-2020 003 cont and c11, 03-03-2020 004 PIR c1, 4-06-2020 003 cont and c1, 4-06-2020 004 PIR c19, 4-06-2020 003 cont and c19, 4-06-2020 004 PIR c1, 5-06-2020 002 cont and c1, 5-06-2020 003 PIR c3, 5-06-2020 001 cont and c3, 5-06-2020 002 PIR</p> <p>c4, 19-06-2020 003 cont and c4, 19-06-2020 004 PIR c5, 19-06-2020 003 cont and c5, 19-06-2020 004 PIR c2, 28-02-2020 019 cont and c2, 28-02-2020 020 PIR</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 4-06-2020 003.axgd • c1, 5-06-2020 002.axgd • c1, 4-06-2020 004.axgd • c1, 5-06-2020 003.axgd • c2, 28-02-2020 019.axgd • c2, 28-02-2020 020.axgd • c3, 03-03-2020 004.axgd • c3, 03-03-2020 005.axgd • c3, 5-06-2020 001.axgd • c3, 5-06-2020 002.axgd • c4, 19-06-2020 003.axgd • c4, 19-06-2020 004.axgd • c5, 19-06-2020 003.axgd • c5, 19-06-2020 004.axgd • c11, 03-03-2020 003.axgd • c11, 03-03-2020 004.axgd • c12, 04-02-2020 003.axgd • c12, 04-02-2020 004.axgd • c19, 4-06-2020 003.axgd • c19, 4-06-2020 004.axgd
6C	<p>c1, 26/6/2020, in NAM, light 50% @ t=15s c1, 26-06-2020 001: episodes 1-12 control episodes 20-31 XE-991 c1, 26-06-2020 002 : washout (episodes 10-21)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 26-06-2020 001.axgd • c1, 26-06-2020 002.axgd • Fig.6C histograms.xlsx
6D	<p>8 cells in dlx, 6 cells in ChAT. Control = NAM Dlx: c1, 26-06-2020 001 (1-12 cont; 20-31 XE; light 50%) c2, 26-06-2020 001 (1-12 cont; 19-30 XE; light 100%) c1, 24-06-2020 003 (1-12 cont; 18-29 XE; light 50%) c2, 24-06-2020 003 (1-12 cont; 21-32 XE; light 100%) c2, 23-06-2020 001 (1-12 cont; 18-30 XE; light 50%) c1, 23-06-2020 001 (1-10 cont; 18-27 XE; light 50%) c2, 12-03-2020 002 (1-12 cont; 16-27 XE; light 75%) c4, 12-03-2020 001 (1-15 cont; 31-45 XE; light 75%)</p> <p>ChAT: c1, 9-06-2021 001 (1-12 cont; 24-35 XE; light 75%) c2, 9-06-2021 001 (1-12 cont; 24-36 XE; light 75%) c3, 9-06-2021 001 (1-12 cont; 24-36 XE; light 75%) C1, 10-06-2021 001 (1-13 cont; 28-40 XE; light 75%) C2, 10-06-2021 001 (1-13 cont; 34-46 XE; light 75%) C3, 10-06-2021 001 (1-13 cont; 35-47 XE; light 75%)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fig.6D basal and post stim spike Fq per episode.xlsx • raw data for Fig.6d: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 9-06-2021 001.axgd • C1, 10-06-2021 001.axgd • c1, 23-06-2020 002.axgd • c1, 24-06-2020 003.axgd • C2, 9-06-2021 001.axgd • C2, 10-06-2021 001.axgd • c2, 12-03-2020 002.axgd • c2, 23-06-2020 001.axgd • c2, 24-06-2020 001.axgd • c2, 26-06-2020 001.axgd • C3, 09-06-2021 001.axgd • C3, 10-06-2021 001.axgd • c4, 12-03-2020 001.axgd
6E - 6F	Same cells as above	Fig.6E-F CTL vs. XE-991 data points.xlsx

Figure 6, figure supplement 1 (RNAscope data)

panel	description	Source file
Fig6 sup1A	Confocal image 20X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fig6 sup1A Experiment_001 8-12-21.lif

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fig6 sup1A Experiment_001.lif - Series003 (RGB)-2.tif
Fig6 sup1B	<p>Fluorescence measure in 6 confocal images</p> <p>Fig6 sup1B Composite 10-12 003 serie 002.tif</p> <p>Fig6 sup1B Composite 10-12 002 serie 011.tif</p> <p>Fig6 sup1B Composite_8-12 001 Series003.tif</p> <p>Fig6 sup1B Composite_8-12 001 Series009.tif</p> <p>Fig6 sup1B Composite_8-12 003 Series010.tif</p> <p>Fig6 sup1B Composite_8-12 003 Series016.tif</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fig6 sup1B normalized fluorescence intensity.xlsx Fig6 sup1B Experiment_8-12 001.lif Fig6 sup1B Experiment_8-12 003.lif Fig6 sup1B Experiment_10-12 002.lif Fig6 sup1B Experiment_10-12 003.lif
Fig6 sup1C	<p>Confocal images 63X:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fig6 sup1C 15-12 exp1 serie 049 GL Composite (RGB).tif Fig6 sup1C 15-12 exp1 serie 055 GCL Composite (RGB).tif 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fig6 sup1C Experiment_001.lif
Fig6 sup1D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 20 confocal images of the glomerular layer (GL) were analyzed 16 confocal images of the granule cell layer (GCL) were analyzed <p>All from 3 mice (8511, 8515, 8517) at 3 different dates (8, 10 and 15 dec 2021)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fig6 sup1D 8-12 Experiment_002.lif Fig6 sup1D 8-12 Experiment003.lif Fig6 sup1D 10-12 Experiment_001.lif Fig6 sup1D 10-12 Experiment_002.lif Fig6 sup1D 10-12 Experiment_003.lif Fig6 sup1D 15-12 Experiment_001.lif Fig6 sup1D 15-12 Experiment_002.lif Fig6 sup1D 15-12 Experiment_003.lif Fig6 sup1D 15-12 Experiment_004.lif <p>Data points and details in: Fig6 sup1D dots per cell.xlsx</p>
Fig6 sup1E	Fig6 sup1E 15-12 exp1 serie50 Composite CR-Chrm1 (RGB).tif	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> raw data in Fig6 sup1D 15-12 Experiment_001.lif /series 050
Fig6 sup1F	15-12 exp2 serie15 Composite TH-Chrm1 (RGB).tif	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> raw data in Fig6 sup1D 15-12 Experiment_002.lif /series 015

Figure 7

panel	description	Source file
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7A	sTC: sTC1, 5/5/21 eTC: c3, 15/12/20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fig.7A Experiment_002 s1, 5-5-21.lif • Fig.7A Experiment_003 s1, 15-12-20.lif
7B	sTC2, 4/5/2021 c2, 04-05-2021 003: control, light 50%, Vh=0mV c2, 04-05-2021 006: +PIR, light 50%, Vh=0mV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fig.7B data points for histograms.xlsx • c2, 04-05-2021 003.axgd • c2, 04-05-2021 006.axgd
7C	c3, 15/12/20 c3, 15-12-2020 004 : episodes 1-40 : control no flash in NAM ep 41-80: flash 100% at t=1 in NAM ep 81-end: control no flash in NAM c3, 15-12-2020 006 : episodes 1-40 : control no flash in NAM+PIR ep 41-80: flash 100% at t=1 in NAM+PIR ep 81-end: control no flash in NAM+PIR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c3, 15-12-2020 004.axgd • c3, 15-12-2020 006.axgd
7D	Mean $\pm$ sem for 17 cells (superficial, middle or external tufted cells) in control condition (i.e. NBQX, DAP5 and mecamlamine). Cells included: eTC4, 12-12-2019 004, Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s sTC4, 14-12-2020 005, Vh=+10mV, light 100% @ t=5s eTC5, 14-12-2020 004, Vh=+10mV, light 100% @ t=5s (ep2-16) eTc3, 15-12-2020 003 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s eTc5, 15-12-2020 002 Vh=+10mV, light 100% @ t=5s mTc2, 04-05-2021 003 Vh=0mV, light 50% @ t=5s mTc7, 04-05-2021 002 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s sTc3, 05-05-2021 002 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s sTc7, 05-05-2021 002 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s eTc1, 11-05-2021 007 Vh=0mV, light 75% @ t=5s eTc2, 11-05-2021 005 Vh=0mV, light 50% @ t=5s sTc4, 11-05-2021 005 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s eTc5, 11-05-2021 004 Vh=0mV, light 50% @ t=5s eTc1, 12-05-2021 005 Vh=0mV, light 50% @ t=5s sTc2, 12-05-2021 005 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s (ep2-15) eTc5, 12-05-2021 003 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s mTc6, 12-05-2021 005 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s Mean $\pm$ sem for 11 cells in NAM+PIRENZEPINE. Cells included: eTC5, 14-12-2020 007, Vh=+10mV, light 100% @ t=5s (ep2-22) c3, 15-12-2020 005, Vh=0mV, light 100% c5, 15-12-2020 004, Vh=+10mV, light 100% c2, 04-05-2021 006, Vh=0mV, light 50% @ t=5s c7, 05-05-2021 008 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s eTc1, 11-05-2021 009 Vh=0mV, light 75% @ t=5s eTc2, 11-05-2021 008 Vh=0mV, light 50% @ t=5s sTc4, 11-05-2021 010 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s eTc5, 11-05-2021 008 Vh=0mV, light 50% @ t=5s eTc5, 12-05-2021 008 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s mTc6, 12-05-2021 009 Vh=0mV, light 100% @ t=5s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figure 7D Data points.xlsx • c4, 12-12-2019 004.axgd • c4, 14-12-2020 005.axgd • c5, 14-12-2020 004.axgd • c5, 14-12-2020 007.axgd • c3, 15-12-2020 003.axgd • c3, 15-12-2020 005.axgd • c5, 15-12-2020 002.axgd • c5, 15-12-2020 004.axgd • c2, 04-05-2021 003.axgd • c2, 04-05-2021 006.axgd • c7, 04-05-2021 002.axgd • c3, 05-05-2021 002.axgd • c7, 05-05-2021 002.axgd • c7, 05-05-2021 008.axgd • c1, 11-05-2021 007.axgd • c1, 11-05-2021 009.axgd • c2, 11-05-2021 005.axgd • c2, 11-05-2021 008.axgd • c4, 11-05-2021 005.axgd • c4, 11-05-2021 010.axgd • c5, 11-05-2021 004.axgd • c5, 11-05-2021 008.axgd • c1, 12-05-2021 005.axgd • c2, 12-05-2021 005.axgd • c5, 12-05-2021 003.axgd • c5, 12-05-2021 008.axgd • c6, 12-05-2021 005.axgd • c6, 12-05-2021 009.axgd
7E	Mean $\pm$ sem for 18 cells (superficial, middle or external tufted cells) in control condition (i.e.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figure 7E data points.xlsx • c3, 15-12-2020 004.axgd

<p>NBQX, DAP5 and mecamylamine). Cells included:</p> <p>eTC3, 15-12-2020 004 1-40 no flash / 41-80 flash 100% / 81-end no flash</p> <p>eTc5, 15-12-2020 003 1-40 no flash / 41-80 flash 100% / 81-end no flash</p> <p>sTc4, 14-12-2020 006 1-40 no flash / 41-end flash 100%</p> <p>eTc5, 14-12-2020 005 1-40 no flash / 41-end flash 100% / 81-120 no flash</p> <p>sTc3, 05-05-2021 003 1-40 no flash / 41-90 flash 100% / 91-140 no flash / 141-end flash 100%</p> <p>sTc4, 05-05-2021 004 1-40 no flash / 41-90 flash 100% / 91-end no flash</p> <p>mTc5, 05-05-2021 002 1-40 no flash / 41-90 flash 100% / 91-140 no flash / 141-end flash 100%</p> <p>sTc7, 05-05-2021 004 1-40 no flash / 41-90 flash 100% / 91-141 no flash / 142-end flash 100%</p> <p>eTc1, 11-05-2021 005 1-40 no flash / 41-80 flash 75% / 81-140 no flash / 141-end flash 100%</p> <p>eTc2, 11-05-2021 003 1-40 no flash / 41-80 flash 100% / 81-120 no flash / 121-end flash 50%</p> <p>eTc5, 11-05-2021 003 1-40 no flash / 41-80 flash 50%</p> <p>eTc1, 12-05-2021 003 1-60 no flash / 11-101 flash 50% / 102-end no flash</p> <p>eTc5, 12-05-2021 002 1-40 no flash / 41-80 flash 100% / 81-end no flash</p> <p>mTc2, 04-05-2021 002 1-40 no flash / 41-end flash 50%</p> <p>mTc7, 04-05-2021 003 1-40 no flash / 41-100 flash 100% / 101-end no flash</p> <p>sTc4, 11-05-2021 003 1-40 no flash / 41-80 flash 100% / 81-end no flash</p> <p>sTc2, 12-05-2021 003 1-40 no flash / 41-80 flash 75% / 81-120 no flash / 121-160 flash 100%</p> <p>mTc6, 12-05-2021 003 1-40 no flash / 41-80 flash 100% / 81-120 no flash</p> <p>Mean $\pm$ sem for 15 cells in NAM+PIRENZEPINE.</p> <p>Cells included:</p> <p>eTC3, 15-12-2020 006 1-40 no flash / 41-80 flash 100% / 81-end no flash</p> <p>eTc5, 15-12-2020 003 1-40 no flash / 41-80 flash 100% / 81-end no flash</p> <p>sTc4, 14-12-2020 007 1-40 no flash / 41-end flash 100%</p> <p>eTc5, 14-12-2020 005 1-40 no flash / 41-end flash 100%</p> <p>sTc4, 05-05-2021 008 1-40 no flash / 41-95 flash 100% / 96-end no flash</p> <p>sTc7, 05-05-2021 006 1-40 no flash / 41-end flash 100%</p> <p>eTc1, 11-05-2021 011 1-40 no flash / 41-end flash 100%</p> <p>eTc2, 11-05-2021 007 1-40 no flash / 41-end flash 50%</p> <p>eTc5, 11-05-2021 006 1-50 no flash / 51-72 flash 50% / 73-120 no flash / 121-160 flash 50%</p> <p>eTc5, 12-05-2021 005 1-60 no flash / 61-101 flash 100% / 102-end no flash</p> <p>mTc2, 04-05-2021 005 1-40 no flash / 41-end flash 50%</p> <p>mTc7, 04-05-2021 005 1-40 no flash / 41-end flash 100%</p> <p>sTc4, 11-05-2021 007 1-40 no flash / 41-95 flash 100% / 96-end no flash</p> <p>sTc2, 12-05-2021 007 1-60 no flash / 61-100 flash 100%</p> <p>mTc6, 12-05-2021 007 1-40 no flash / 41-50 flash 100% / 51-100 no flash / 101-140 flash 100% / 141-end no flash</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c3, 15-12-2020 006.axgd • c5, 15-12-2020 003.axgd • c5, 15-12-2020 005.axgd • c4, 14-12-2020 006.axgd • c4, 14-12-2020 007.axgd • c5, 14-12-2020 005.axgd • c5, 14-12-2020 006.axgd • c3, 05-05-2021 003.axgd • c4, 05-05-2021 004.axgd • c4, 05-05-2021 008.axgd • c5, 05-05-2021 002.axgd • c7, 05-05-2021 004.axgd • c7, 05-05-2021 006.axgd • c1, 11-05-2021 005.axgd • c1, 11-05-2021 011.axgd • c2, 11-05-2021 003.axgd • c2, 11-05-2021 007.axgd • c5, 11-05-2021 003.axgd • c5, 11-05-2021 006.axgd • c1, 12-05-2021 003.axgd • c5, 12-05-2021 002.axgd • c5, 12-05-2021 005.axgd • c2, 04-05-2021 002.axgd • c2, 04-05-2021 005.axgd • c7, 04-05-2021 003.axgd • c7, 04-05-2021 005.axgd • c4, 11-05-2021 003.axgd • c4, 11-05-2021 007.axgd • c2, 12-05-2021 003.axgd • c2, 12-05-2021 007.axgd • c6, 12-05-2021 003.axgd • c6, 12-05-2021 007.axgd
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Figure 8

panel	description	Source file
8A	<p>Example : cell 6, 6/3/2019 (see cell 6, 6-03-2019 001.axgd for raw data)</p> <p>Cells included in the analysis (n=28) with flash at t=1s:</p> <p>cell4 08052017 002: light 100%</p> <p>cell9 08052017 001: light 100% ep 1-50, no light ep 51-end</p> <p>cell10 08052017 001: no light 1-35, light 100 % 36-91</p> <p>cell11 08052017 001: light 100% ep 1-50, no light 51-end</p> <p>cell20 08052017 001; no light 1-50, light 100 % 51-end</p> <p>cell13, 13072017 002: light 100%</p> <p>cell20, 18072017 002: light 100%</p> <p>cell15, 24072017 001: light 100% ep 1-39, 40-end no flash</p> <p>cell16, 24072017 001: no light 1-30, light 100 % 31-end</p> <p>cell 12, 13-02-2019 002: light 50%</p> <p>cell 16, 13-02-2019 004: : light 50%</p> <p>cell 23, 13-02-2019 002: light 50% ep 1-61</p> <p>cell 25, 13-02-2019 001: light 50% ep 1-50, no light 51-end</p> <p>cell 26, 13-02-2019 001: light 50% ep 1-54</p> <p>cell 2, 14-02-2019 002: light 70% ep 1-72</p> <p>cell 4, 14-02-2019 001: light 50% ep 1-40</p> <p>cell 5, 14-02-2019 001: light 50% ep 1-65</p> <p>cell 13, 5-03-2019 001: light 50% ep 1-70</p> <p>cell 3, 6-03-2019 002: light 100% ep 1-60</p> <p>cell 1, 6-03-2019 001: light 50% ep 1-44</p> <p>c3, 15-07-2020 001: no light 1-39, light 50 % 40-end</p> <p>c5, 8-12-2020 001: no light 1-30, light 50 % 31-end</p> <p>c3, 17-12-2020 019: no light 1-30, light 50 % 31-end</p> <p>c2, 18-12-2020 009: no light 1-30, light 60 % 31-end</p> <p>c3, 18-12-2020 001: no light 1-30, light 60 % 31-end</p> <p>c1, 21-12-2020 010: no light 1-30, light 70 % 31-end</p> <p>c2, 21-12-2020 021: no light 1-30, light 90 % 31-end</p> <p>c4, 21-12-2020 044: no light 1-40, light 75 % 41-end</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Figure 8A histogram cell 6, 6-3-2019 ACSF.xlsx • Figure 8A average inhibition time course n=28 ACSF.xlsx • raw data : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cell4 08052017 002.axgd • cell9 08052017 001.axgd • cell10 08052017 001.axgd • cell11 08052017 001.axgd • cell20 08052017 001.axgd • cell13, 13072017 002.axgd • cell20, 18072017 002.axgd • cell15, 24072017 001.axgd • cell16, 24072017 001.axgd • cell 12, 13-02-2019 002.axgd • cell 16, 13-02-2019 004.axgd • cell 23, 13-02-2019 002.axgd • cell 25, 13-02-2019 001.axgd • cell 26, 13-02-2019 001.axgd • cell 2, 14-02-2019 002.axgd • cell 4, 14-02-2019 001.axgd • cell 5, 14-02-2019 001.axgd • cell 13, 5-03-2019 001.axgd • cell 3, 6-03-2019 002.axgd • cell 1, 6-03-2019 001.axgd • c3, 15-07-2020 001.axgd • c5, 8-12-2020 001.axgd • c3, 17-12-2020 019.axgd • c2, 18-12-2020 009.axgd • c3, 18-12-2020 001.axgd • c1, 21-12-2020 010.axgd • c2, 21-12-2020 021.axgd • c4, 21-12-2020 044.axgd
8B	<p>Example : c6, 6/3/2019</p> <p>7 cells included in the analysis :</p> <p>cell 6, 6-03-2019 003 : light 50% in NAM</p> <p>cell 6, 6-03-2019 004 : light 50% in NAM+GBZ</p> <p>cell 3, 6-03-2019 004 : light 50% in NAM</p> <p>cell 3, 6-03-2019 005 : light 50% in NAM+GBZ</p> <p>cell 2, 6-03-2019 001: light 50% in NAM</p> <p>cell 2, 6-03-2019 003: light 50% in NAM+GBZ (ep 80-end)</p> <p>cell 11, 5-03-2019 002: light 50% in NAM</p> <p>cell 11, 5-03-2019 003: light 50% in NAM+GBZ (ep 70-end)</p> <p>cell 16, 5-03-2019 001: light 50% in NAM</p> <p>cell 16, 5-03-2019 004: light 50% in NAM+GBZ</p> <p>cell 5, 14-02-2019 001: light 50% in ACSF</p> <p>cell 5, 14-02-2019 003: light 50% in ACSF+GBZ</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fig.8B data for histograms cell6 6-3-2019.xlsx • Fig.8B data for 7 cells CTL vs. GBZ.xlsx raw data : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cell 6, 6-03-2019 003.axgd • cell 6, 6-03-2019 004.axgd • cell 3, 6-03-2019 004.axgd • cell 3, 6-03-2019 005.axgd • cell 2, 6-03-2019 001.axgd • cell 2, 6-03-2019 003.axgd • cell 11, 5-03-2019 002.axgd

	<p>c3, 17-12-2020 022: in NAM, no light 1-30, light 50% 31-end c3, 17-12-2020 024: in NAM+GBZ, no light 1-30, light 50% 31-end</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cell 11, 5-03-2019 003.axgd • cell 16, 5-03-2019 001.axgd • cell 16, 5-03-2019 004.axgd • cell 5, 14-02-2019 001.axgd • cell 5, 14-02-2019 003.axgd • c3, 17-12-2020 022.axgd • c3, 17-12-2020 024.axgd
8C	<p>Distribution of spike inhibition duration type 2.2 PG cells vs. type 2.3 PG cells From same recordings as in Fig.8A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fig.8C Data first spike timing type 2.2.xlsx • Fig.8C Data first spike timing type 2.3.xlsx
8D	<p>Example: cell7, 16-5-2019 cell 7, 16-5-2019 001, 0-30 no flash; 31-69 light 100% cell 7, 16-5-2019 002, flash 100% @ t=5s cell 7, 16-5-2019 003, flash 100% @ t=5s, Vh=-35 mV, immediately after break-in cell 7, 16-5-2019 004, flash 100% @ t=5s, Vh=0 mV cell 7, 16-5-2019 006, ON stim @ t=1s, Vh=-75 mV cell 7, 16-5-2019 007 and 008, CClamp current steps</p>	<p>Figure 8D, data for histogram.xlsx</p> <p>Recordings from c7, 16-5-2019</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cell 7, 16-5-2019 001.axgd • cell 7, 16-5-2019 002.axgd • cell 7, 16-5-2019 003.axgd • cell 7, 16-5-2019 004.axgd • cell 7, 16-5-2019 005.axgd • cell 7, 16-5-2019 006.axgd • cell 7, 16-5-2019 007.axgd • cell 7, 16-5-2019 008.axgd <p>Raw data for histogram</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c1, 21-12-2020 014.axgd • cell 7, 22-03-2019 004.axgd • c4, 7-07-2020 005.axgd • cell 7, 16-5-2019 004.axgd • c3, 15-07-2020 007.axgd • cell 4, 21-03-2019 004.axgd • cell5 22032017 005.axgd
Sup. 1	<p>Recordings for sup.1A (n=17): Same as in Fig.8A</p> <p>Recordings for sup.1B (n=18): Cell 4 08052017 003, flash 100% @ t=5 cell 9 08052017 002, ep 1-4 no flash, ep 5-9 flash 100% cell 16, 24072017 003, flash 100% cell 11, 13-02-2019 003, flash 100% cell 12, 13-02-2019 003, flash 50% cell 15, 13-02-2019 004, flash 50% cell 16, 13-02-2019 003, flash 50% cell 23, 13-02-2019 003, flash 50% cell 26, 13-02-2019 002, flash 50% cell 2, 14-02-2019 001, flash 70% cell 4, 14-02-2019 002, flash 50% cell 5, 14-02-2019 002, flash 50% cell 13, 5-03-2019 002, flash 50% cell 3, 6-03-2019 003, flash 100% cell 6, 6-03-2019 002, flash 50% c3, 17-12-2020 021, flash 50% c2, 18-12-2020 010, flash 60% c2, 21-12-2020 022, flash 90%</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • data for Fig.8 sup 1A.xlsx • data for Fig.8 sup 1B.xlsx <p>recordings for fig.1B :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cell 4 08052017 003.axgd • cell 9 08052017 002.axgd • cell 16, 24072017 003.axgd • cell 11, 13-02-2019 003.axgd • cell 12, 13-02-2019 003.axgd • cell 15, 13-02-2019 004.axgd • cell 16, 13-02-2019 003.axgd • cell 23, 13-02-2019 003.axgd • cell 26, 13-02-2019 002.axgd • cell 2, 14-02-2019 001.axgd • cell 4, 14-02-2019 002.axgd • cell 5, 14-02-2019 002.axgd • cell 13, 5-03-2019 002.axgd • cell 3, 6-03-2019 003.axgd

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> cell 6, 6-03-2019 002.axgd c3, 17-12-2020 021.axgd c2, 18-12-2020 010.axgd c2, 21-12-2020 022
Sup. 2	<p><u>Left</u>: c5, 8-12-2020 001: no light 1-30, light 50 % 31-end</p> <p><u>Middle</u>: c3, 15-07-2020 001: no light 1-39, light 50 % 40-end</p> <p><u>Right</u>: cell 4, 14-02-2019 001: light 50% ep 1-40</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> raw data same as in Fig.8A Fig.8 sup fig.2 data firing rate vs first spike timing.xlsx

Figure 9

panel	description	Source file
9A	Cell 2, 9/12/2020 c2, 9-12-2020 001 : ACSF, 1-30 no flash, 31-end flash 50%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c2, 9-12-2020 001.axgd
9B	Same cell c2, 9-12-2020 003 : NAM, 1-30 no flash, 31-end flash 50% c2, 9-12-2020 004 : NAM+GBZ, 1-30 no flash, 31-end flash 50% c2, 9-12-2020 007 : after 20 min washout in NAM, flash 50%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c2, 9-12-2020 003.axgd c2, 9-12-2020 004.axgd c2, 9-12-2020 007.axgd
9C	Cell 4, 9/12/2020 C4, 9-12-2020 001 : ACSF, 1-30 no flash, 31-end flash 70%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C4, 9-12-2020 001.axgd
9D	Same cell C4, 9-12-2020 002 : NAM, 1-40 flash 70%, 41-end no flash C4, 9-12-2020 003 : NAM+GBZ, 1-50 flash 70%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C4, 9-12-2020 002.axgd C4, 9-12-2020 003.axgd
9E	<p>Light-evoked inward current + spikes</p> <p>cell8 28032017 001, , ACSF, flash 100% @t=0.5s cell20 30032017 001, ACSF, flash 100% c2, 29-5-2018 001, NAM, 1-50 flash 50%, 51-end no flash cell 14, 13-02-2019 002, ACSF, flash 50% c2, 4-06-2020 001, ACSF, 1-25 no flash, 26-end flash 50% c1, 2-07-2020 001, ACSF, flash 50% c3, 2-07-2020 001, ACSF, flash 75% c3, 9-07-2020 001, ACSF, flash 50% c1, 8-12-2020 000, ACSF, 1-30 no flash, 31-end flash 50% c1, 9-12-2020 006, ACSF, 1-11 no flash, 12-end flash 50% c2, 9-12-2020 see above figure 9A and 9B c17, 9-12-2020 017, ACSF, flash 70% c5, 18-12-2020 044, ACSF, 1-30 no flash, 31-end flash 60% c4, 22-12-2020 022, ACSF, 1-27 no flash, 28-end flash 50%</p> <p>Light-evoked outward current + spikes</p> <p>C3, 29-5-2018 001, NAM, 1-32 flash 50%, 33-61 no flash, 62-end flash 50% c4, 24-5-2018 001, ACSF, flash 50% cell 3, 14-02-2019 001, ACSF, flash 50% cell 17, 5-03-2019 001, ACSF, flash 90% cell4, 25072017 002, ACSF, flash 100% cell9, 25072017 001, ACSF, flash 100% cell4, 24072017 001, ACSF, flash 100% cell15, 18072017 002, ACSF, flash 100% cell19 08052017 002, ACSF, 1-57 flash 100%, 58-end no flash cell21 08052017 001, ACSF, 1-45 flash 100%, 46-end no flash cell9 28032017 001, ACSF, 1-40 flash 100% @t=0.5s, 41-70 no flash, 71-end flash 100% cell 1, 12-03-2019 003, ACSF, flash 100% c4, 9-12-2020 001 (see in Fig.9C and 9D)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> data fig.9E.xlsx raw data : <p>cell8 28032017 001.axgd cell20 30032017 001.axgd c2, 29-5-2018 001.axgd cell 14, 13-02-2019 002.axgd c2, 4-06-2020 001.axgd c1, 2-07-2020 001.axgd c3, 2-07-2020 001.axgd c3, 9-07-2020 001.axgd c1, 8-12-2020 000.axgd c1, 9-12-2020 006.axgd c2, 9-12-2020 see above figure 9A and 9B c17, 9-12-2020 017.axgd c5, 18-12-2020 044.axgd c4, 22-12-2020 022.axgd C3, 29-5-2018 001.axgd C3, 29-5-2018 001.axgd c4, 24-5-2018 001.axgd cell 3, 14-02-2019 001.axgd cell 17, 5-03-2019 001.axgd cell4, 25072017 002.axgd cell9, 25072017 001.axgd cell4, 24072017 001.axgd cell15, 18072017 002.axgd cell19 08052017 002.axgd cell21 08052017 001.axgd cell9 28032017 001.axgd cell 1, 12-03-2019 003.axgd c4, 9-12-2020 001 (see in Fig.9C and 9D) c1, 22-12-2020 004.axgd c2, 22-12-2020 009.axgd</p>

	<p>c1, 22-12-2020 004, ACSF, flash 75%</p> <p>c2, 22-12-2020 009, ACSF, 1-30 no flash, 31-end flash 50%</p>	<p>c4, 24-5-2018 001.axgd</p> <p>cell 3, 14-02-2019 001.axgd</p> <p>cell 17, 5-03-2019 001.axgd</p> <p>cell4, 25072017 002.axgd</p> <p>cell9, 25072017 001.axgd</p> <p>cell4, 24072017 001.axgd</p> <p>cell15, 18072017 002.axgd</p> <p>cell19 08052017 002.axgd</p> <p>cell21 08052017 001.axgd</p> <p>cell9 28032017 001.axgd</p> <p>cell 1 , 12-03-2019 003.axgd</p> <p>c4, 9-12-2020 001 (see in Fig.9C and 9D)</p> <p>c1, 22-12-2020 004.axgd</p> <p>c2, 22-12-2020 009.axgd</p>
9F	<p>n=14 cells with light-evoked inward current + spikes (same as in Fig.9E) + n=38 cells with light-evoked inward current but no spike:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cell 11, 15/3/2017 (X023904 page 72, 001) few spike, light-evoked inward current <2 pA 2. Cell 12, 15/3/2017 (X023904 page 72, 001) few spike, light-evoked inward current <1 pA 3. Cell 10, 28/3/2017 (X023904 page 87, 001) (0.47 Hz) few spike, light-evoked inward current <1 pA 4. Cell 15, 30/3/2017 (X023904 page 91, 002) no spike, light-evoked inward current <2 pA 5. Cell 6, 8/5/2017 (X023904 page 112) no spike, light-evoked inward current <1 pA 6. Cell 14, 8/5/2017 (X023904 page 114) no spike but small inward current <1 pA 7. Cell 10, 18/7/2017 (X023904 page 136) (0.08 Hz) but small inward current <1 pA 8. Cell 16, 18/7/2017 (X023904 page 138) (0.22 Hz) small inward current <2 pA 9. Cell 8, 24/7/2017 (X023904 page 141) (0.02 Hz) small inward current <1 pA 10. Cell 3, 25/7/2017 (X023904 page 143) no spike but light-evoked inward current 3 pA and OSN-evoked spiking compatible with CR 11. Cell 18, 13/2/2019 (X081359 page 23) 4-5 Hz, light-induced inward current 1 pA 12. Cell 2, 5/3/2019 (X081359 page 33) no spike, light-induced inward current 4 pA 13. Cell 18, 4/6/2020 (X081359 page 150) no spike, small inward current 1 pA 14. Cell x3, 8/12/20 (X081359 page 191) no spike, small inward current 15. Cell x4, 8/12/20 (X081359 page 191) no spike, small inward current 16. Cell x5, 8/12/20 (X081359 page 191) no spike, small inward current 17. Cell x6, 8/12/20 (X081359 page 191) no spike, small inward current 18. Cell x8, 8/12/20 (X081359 page 191) no spike, small inward current 19. Cell x12, 8/12/20 (X081359 page 191) no spike, small inward current 	Raw data on demand

20. Cell x14, 8/12/20 (X081359 page 191) no spike, small inward current
21. Cell x12, 9/12/20 (X081359 page 194) no spike, small inward current (-1.5 pA)
22. Cell x16, 9/12/20 (X081359 page 195) no spike, small inward current (-1 pA)
23. Cell x18, 9/12/20 (X081359 page 195) no spike, small inward current (-2 pA)
24. Cell x19, 9/12/20 (X081359 page 195) no spike, small inward current (-1 pA)
25. Cell x3, 16/12/20 (X023894 page 15) no spike, inward current (<1 pA)
26. Cell x4, 16/12/20 (X023894 page 15) no spike, inward current (<1 pA)
27. Cell x17, 16/12/20 (X023894 page 16) no spike, inward current (3 pA)
28. Cell x25, 16/12/20 (X023894 page 16) no spike, inward current (2 pA)
29. Cell x3, 17/12/20 (X023894 page 18) no spike, inward current (2 pA)
30. Cell x10, 17/12/20 (X023894 page 19) no spike, inward current (2 pA)
31. Cell x11, 17/12/20 (X023894 page 20) no spike, inward current (<2 pA)
32. Cell x12, 17/12/20 (X023894 page 20) no spike, inward current (<2 pA)
33. Cell x8, 18/12/20 (X023894 page 21) no spike, inward current (1 pA)
34. Cell x9, 18/12/20 (X023894 page 21) no spike, inward current (2 pA)
35. Cell x12, 18/12/20 (X023894 page 21) no spike, inward current (1 pA)
36. Cell x18, 18/12/20 (X023894 page 22) no spike, inward current (1 pA)
37. Cell x28, 18/12/20 (X023894 page 22) no spike, inward current (1 pA)
38. Cell x9, 21/12/20 (X023894 page 24) no spike inward current 2 pA

n=15 cells with light-evoked outward current + spikes (same as in Fig.9E) + n=32 cells with light evoked outward current but no spike:

1. Cell 8, 14/3/2017 (X023904 page 67, 001) (no spike but light-evoked outward current 54 pA)
2. Cell 9, 14/3/2017 (X023904 page 67, 001) (no spike but light-evoked outward current 14 pA)
3. Cell 4, 28/3/2017 (X023904 page 85, 001) (0.02 Hz, but light-evoked outward current 8 pA)
4. Cell 5, 28/3/2017 (X023904 page 86, 001) (0.05 Hz but light-evoked outward current 46 pA)
5. Cell 19, 30/3/2017 (X023904 page 92, 005) few spikes but light-evoked outward current 19 pA

	<ol style="list-style-type: none">6. Cell 8, 6/4/2017 (X023904 page 98) no spike but light-evoked outward current 5 pA7. Cell 17, 8/5/2017 (X023904 page 114) no spike but light-evoked outward current 5.5 pA8. Cell 5, 13/7/2017 (X023904 page 133) few spikes, light-evoked outward current 5 pA9. Cell 17, 18/7/2017 (X023904 page 139) (no spike) light-evoked outward current10. Cell 7, 25/7/2017 (X023904 page 144) no spike but light-evoked outward-inward current 3 pA11. Cell 10, 25/7/2017 (X023904 page 145) but light-evoked outward current 30 pA12. Cell 13, 23/5/2018 (Z035040 page 16) (no spike) outward current 3 pA13. Cell 14, 23/5/2018 (Z035040 page 16) (no spike) outward current 4 pA14. Cell 19, 23/5/2018 (Z035040 page 17) (no spike) outward current 3 pA15. Cell 1, 13/2/2019 (X081359 page 21) no spike, outward current <5pA16. Cell 5, 13/2/2019 (X081359 page 21) few spike, outward current 9 pA17. Cell 3, 5/3/2019 (X081359 page 33) few spikes, outward current 1 pA18. Cell 4, 5/3/2019 (X081359 page 33) few spikes, outward current 1 pA19. Cell 1, 6/3/2019 (X081359 page 36) outward current 15-30pA20. Cell 4, 6/3/2019 (X081359 page 37) outward current in some trials21. Cell 5, 6/3/2019 (X081359 page 37) outward current 12 pA22. Cell 4, 4/6/2020 (X081359 page 148) no spike, outward current 5 pA23. Cell 5, 4/6/2020 (X081359 page 148) no spike, outward current 10 pA24. Cell 8, 4/6/2020 (X081359 page 149) no spike, outward current 17 pA25. Cell x3, 9/12/20 (X081359 page 193) no spike, small outward current26. Cell x4, 9/12/20 (X081359 page 193) no spike, small outward current27. Cell x20, 9/12/20 (X081359 page 195) no spike, outward current (>10 pA)28. Cell x21, 18/12/20 (X023894 page 22) no spike, outward current 30 pA29. Cell x22, 18/12/20 (X023894 page 22) no spike, outward current 13 pA30. Cell x11, 21/12/20 (X023894 page 25) no spike outward current 2 pA31. Cell x16, 21/12/20 (X023894 page 25) no spike outward current 4 pA32. Cell x17, 21/12/20 (X023894 page 25) no spike outward current 2 pA	
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9G	<p>Example for illustration: cell 3, 2/7/2020 c3, 2-07-2020 001: LCA, ACSF, light 75% c3, 2-07-2020 003: WC, Vh=0mV, light 75% c3, 2-07-2020 009: WC, C-Clamp, current steps</p> <p>6 additional cells in histogram: c1, 2-07-2020 003: WC, Vh=0mV, light 75% c3, 9-07-2020 005: WC, Vh=0mV, light 50% cell 4, 13-03-2019 010: WC, Vh=0mV, light 50% cell2 140317 005: WC, Vh=0mV, light 100% cell7 04052017 006: WC, Vh=0mV, light 100% cell8 28032017 006: WC, Vh=0mV, light 100%</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • c3, 2-07-2020 001.axgd • c3, 2-07-2020 003.axgd • c3, 2-07-2020 009.axgd • data histogram IPSC decay time constant.xlsx • cell2 140317 005.axgd • c1, 2-07-2020 003.axgd • c3, 9-07-2020 005.axgd • cell 4, 13-03-2019 010.axgd • cell7 04052017 006.axgd • cell8 28032017 006.axgd
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9G	<p>Light-evoked IPSCs in histogram cell2 140317 005, Vh=0mV, flash 100% cell8 28032017 006, Vh=0mV, flash 100% @t=0.5s cell7 04052017 006, Vh=0mV, flash 100% cell 4, 13-03-2019 010, Vh=0mV, flash 50% c1, 2-07-2020 003, Vh=0mV, flash 50% c3, 2-07-2020 003, Vh=0mV, flash 75% c3, 9-07-2020 005, Vh=0mV, flash 50%</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• data histogram IPSC decay time constant.xlsx• cell2 140317 005.axgd• cell8 28032017 006.axgd• cell7 04052017 006.axgd• cell 4, 13-03-2019 010.axgd• c1, 2-07-2020 003.axgd• c3, 2-07-2020 003.axgd• c3, 9-07-2020 005.axgd
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